

Taxonomic Evaluation of Two Coprinoid Fungi of the Genus *Coprinopsis* in Jalna District, Maharashtra (India)

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Abstract:

This study presents the morphological and taxonomic characterization of two coprinoid fungi *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* and *Coprinopsis macrocephala*—collected from Jalna district, Maharashtra, India, during the August 2024 monsoon season. Macroscopic features, including pileus morphology, lamellae, stipe characters, and habitat, were recorded from fresh basidiocarps, while microscopic studies examined basidiospores, basidia, cystidia, and pileipellis structure using standard techniques. *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* was distinguished by larger basidiocarps, a radially fibrillose pileus, and dark brown spores with a prominent germ pore. In contrast, *C. macrocephala* exhibited a conical pileus, veil remnants, and thick-walled basidiospores. Both species showed deliquescent lamellae and saprotrophic growth on nutrient-rich substrates. The study provides baseline taxonomic data contributing to the documentation of coprinoid fungal diversity in the semi-arid region of Maharashtra.

Keywords: *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa*; *Coprinopsis macrocephala*; Coprinoid fungi; Morpho-taxonomy; Basidiomycota; Agaricales.

Introduction:

Fungi are among the most diverse and ecologically essential groups of Eukaryota organisms, playing vital roles in decomposition, nutrient cycling, and ecosystem stability (Atri, 2015; Upadhyay, 2018). Within Basidiomycota, the order Agaricales includes a wide variety of gilled mushrooms with notable morphological diversity and ecological adaptability. Coprinoid fungi, historically classified under *Coprinus* sensu lato, are notable for their autodigesting (deliquescent) gills and short-lived basidiocarps (Redhead et al., 2001; Moncalvo et al., 2002). Molecular phylogenetics have led to their division into genera such as *Coprinopsis*, *Coprinellus*, and *Parasola*, redefining their classification within Psathyrellaceae (Hopple & Vilgalys, 1999; Redhead et al., 2001). The genus *Coprinopsis* is

recognized as a monophyletic group characterized by thin basidiocarps, striate or fibrillose cap surfaces, deliquescent gills, dark brown to black basidiospores with a germ pore, and various veil structures (Kirk et al., 2008; Singer, 1986). These species are mainly saprotrophic, commonly found on dung, compost, decaying plant material, and nutrient-rich soils, playing an important role in breaking down lignocellulosic matter and recycling organic material, especially in agro-ecosystems (Atri, 2015; Kaur & Atri, 2017). Accurate morphotaxonomic identification remains crucial for species delimitation, particularly in areas with limited molecular data (Amandeep et al., 2015; Upadhyay, 2018). Important taxa include *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* Atri, A. Kaur & M. Kaur and *Coprinopsis macrocephala* (Berk.) Redhead,

Vilgalys & Moncalvo. *C. radiata* var. *macrocarpa* was identified based on its larger basidiocarps and unique micromorphological features, such as spore size and pileus structure (Atri, Kaur & Kaur, 2012). *C. macrocephala*, initially classified under *Coprinus*, was reassigned to *Coprinopsis* after thorough morphological review and molecular phylogenetics clarified its position (Redhead et al., 2001; Moncalvo et al., 2002). While coprinoid fungi have been reported from parts of India like Punjab and the Western Ghats, detailed studies on semi-arid ecosystems are scarce (Atri, 2015; Amandeep et al., 2015). The Jalna district in Maharashtra, with its monsoonal climate and agricultural landscapes, offers conducive substrates for coprinoid fungi; however, documentation of *Coprinopsis* species here is limited (Upadhyay, 2018). Hence, this study aims to provide detailed morphological and taxonomic descriptions of *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* and *Coprinopsis macrocephala* from Jalna. This work adds valuable taxonomic data to regional fungal biodiversity records and supports future ecological and systematic research on coprinoid fungi in Maharashtra.

Material and Methods:

Collection:

Samples of *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* and *Coprinopsis macrocephala* were collected in August 2024 from Mantha tahsil in Jalna district, Maharashtra. The locality's GPS coordinates are Lat 19.3857° and Long 76.2313°. During collection, habitat, date, and vegetation type were recorded. To confirm the species' identity, a detailed study of macroscopic and microscopic features was conducted, including descriptions of the pileus (diameter, shape, and colour), cuticle (general and marginal features), lamellae, and stipe (position, shape, length, thickness, and colours).

Taxonomic examination:

The specimens were examined in detail for various macroscopic features, including shape, size, colour, gill type, and margin. Microscopic analysis focused on the hyphal system, basidia, and basidiospores. Morphological traits were compared with standard taxonomic references (Mirdu et al., 2023). Anatomical features, such as hyphae, basidia, and basidiospores and their arrangements, were studied using crush mounts and hand-cut sections. Samples were stained with Congo red, cotton blue, and Melzer's reagent. Photomicrographs of gills, mycelium, and spores were taken, and measurements were performed with an Olympus BX53 microscope. The species has also been reported from Haryana (Kaur et al., 2023).

Results and Discussion:

***Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* Atri. A. Kaur & M. Kaur**

Family: Psathyrellaceae

Macroscopic features: Carpophores: 11-15 cm tall. **Pileus:** 1.6 to 4 cm in height, with a campanulate to conical shape, an umbonate structure, a short umbo, and a scaly pileal veil. The scales are white and abundant, with an irregular margin that is brownish black at the apex. **Lamellae:** free, unequal, crowded, and vary from narrow to moderately broad, all black, with smooth edges. **Stipe:** 10.1-14.4 cm long, 0.6-1 cm wide, tapering upward, with a bulbous base, white, and fibrillose surface. **Microscopic characteristics: Basidiospores:** it measuring 12-16.3 x 5.8-8.1 µm, ellipsoidal, with a germ pore, thick walls, smooth surface, and dark reddish brown to blackish brown colouration. **Basidia:** 11.4-16 x 7.1- 9.4 µm, dimorphic, clavate, elongated cylindrical to clavate, bearing sterigmata. **Cheilocystidia:** 36.5-51 x 16.4-28 µm, ellipsoidal to inflated clavate, thin-walled, hyaline. **Pleurocystidia:** 53.4-78 x 15-26.6 µm,

elongated ellipsoidal to inflated clavate, thin-walled, hyaline. The above macro- and micromorphological features are consistent with the original description of the taxon. **Similar observations were noted by** Atri, N. S. and Kaur, Amandeep (2010), Nagy, L. G. et al. (2012), Keirle, M. R. et al. (2004), and Vellinga, E. C. (2004), who reported comparable pileal veil structure, spore dimensions, dimorphic basidia, and cystidial morphology in coprinoid members of *Coprinopsis*.

***Coprinopsis macrocephala* (Berk.) Redhead, Vilgalys & Moncalvo**

Family: Psathyrellaceae

Macroscopic features: **Carpophores:** it measures 11–15.2 cm in height, Pileus: 1.6–3.1 cm tall. Young fungi are elongated or ellipsoid, becoming convex or flattened as they mature; their surface is moist, blackish grey, with irregular margins. **Lamellae:** free, unequal, crowded, and black. **Stipe:** central is 10.1–14.3 cm long, cylindrical, bulbous at the base, hollow, and white on the surface. **Microscopic features:** **Basidiospores:** it measuring 13–15.6 x 8.8–11

µm, ellipsoidal, with a germ pore, thick walls, smooth surface, dark reddish-brown colouration, and an apiculus. **Basidia:** 30–37 x 13.2–15.2 µm, thin-walled, hyaline, with sterigmata. The gill edges are sterile. **Cheilocystidia:** 38.64 x 18–31 µm, ellipsoidal, clavate, thin-walled, and hyaline. **Pleurocystidia:** 48–98 x 23–43 µm, inflated and clavate, thin-walled, and hyaline. **Pileus cuticle:** unbranched, cylindrical to ellipsoidal, septate. **Clamp connections:** septate, thin-walled, and granular. **Stipe tissue:** it consists of hyphae that are longitudinally tangled, thin-walled, and hyaline. **Clamp connections:** present throughout. The above morphological and microscopic characters conform to earlier descriptions of the species. **Similar observations were noted by** Atri, N. S. (2015), Amandeep Kaur et al. (2015), Redhead, S. A. et al. (2001), Kirk, P. M. et al. (2008), and Uljé, C. B. (2005), who reported comparable macroscopic features, spore dimensions, cystidial structures, and the presence of clamp connections in *Coprinopsis macrocephala*.

A

B

C

D

E

F

Fig 1. *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* Atri. A. Kaur & M. Kaur A, B-C Natural Habitat of Carpophore, D- Basidia, E- Basidiospore, F-Cheilocystidia, G-Pleurocystidia, H- Pileus cuticle.

Fig. 2 *Coprinopsis macrocephala* (Berk.) Redhead, Vilgalys & Moncalvo A, B-C Natural Habitat of Carpophore, D- Basidia, E- Basidiospore, F-Cheilocystidia, G-Pleurocystidia, H- Pileus cuticle.

Conclusion:

The present morpho-taxonomic investigation confirms the occurrence of *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* and *Coprinopsis macrocephala* in Jalna district, Maharashtra, India. Detailed examination of macroscopic and microscopic characters established clear diagnostic distinctions between the two taxa despite their shared placement in the family Psathyrellaceae. *Coprinopsis radiata* var. *macrocarpa* is characterized by comparatively larger carpophores, a scaly white pileal veil with brownish-black apex, dimorphic basidia, and relatively narrower ellipsoidal basidiospores with a distinct germ pore. In contrast, *C. macrocephala* exhibits a moist blackish-grey pileus, sterile gill edges, larger and broader basidiospores with a prominent apiculus, well-developed pleurocystidia, and clamp connections throughout the hyphal system. Differences in cystidial morphology, spore dimensions, pileus cuticle structure, and clamp connection distribution provide reliable taxonomic markers for species delimitation. Both taxa demonstrate typical coprinoid characteristics such as deliquescent lamellae, saprotrophic growth, and adaptation to nutrient-rich substrates. Their documentation from the semi-arid agro-ecosystems of Jalna enriches regional fungal biodiversity records and provides baseline data for future systematic, ecological, and conservation-oriented studies of coprinoid fungi in Maharashtra.

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